

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND TECHNICAL MEANS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND EXPLOITATION OF SHALE GAS FIELDS

Lachezar Georgiev, Martin Boyadzhiev

University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, 1700 Sofia; E-mail: lachezar.georgiev@mgu.bg; martinb@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. The report analyses the modern technologies and technical means for the development and exploitation of shale gas fields. The development of shale gas fields is carried out by drilling several wells with horizontal sections from one working site and applying the hydraulic fracturing technology. In world practice, complex hydromechanical impact in combination with physicochemical impact is widely applied as a highly efficient method in gas extraction from shale gas fields. For each specific shale gas field, the technologies and technical means of development and exploitation must take into account the specific characteristics of the shale formation and the geological conditions.

Key words: shale gas, development, exploitation.

СЪВРЕМЕННИ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКИ СРЕДСТВА ЗА РАЗРАБОТКА И ЕКСПЛОАТАЦИЯ НА НАХОДИЩА НА ШИСТОВ ГАЗ

Лъчезар Георгиев, Мартин Бояджиев

Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София

РЕЗЮМЕ. В доклада е направен анализ на съвременните технологии и технически средства за разработка и експлоатация на находища на шистов газ. Разработването на находища на шистов газ се осъществява чрез прокарването на няколко сондажа с хоризонтални участъци от една работна площадка и прилагането на технологията хидравлично разкъсване. В световната практика като високоефективен метод широко приложение при добива на газ от находища на шистов газ се прилага комплексно хидромеханично и съчетаното с него физикохимично въздействие. При всяко конкретно находище на шистов газ технологиите и техническите средства за разработка и експлоатация трябва да се съобразяват със специфичните характеристики на шистовата формация и геоложките условия.

Ключови думи: шистов газ, разработка, експлоатация.

Introduction

Shale gas is natural gas extracted from deposits composed of clay-rich, low-permeability rocks that either contain gas in a free state or absorb it on clay surfaces. The development of gas deposits containing argillite layers involves the drilling of multiple wells with horizontal sections from a single working site, utilising hydraulic fracturing technology or techniques aimed at enhancing the permeability of the argillite layer. The design of the wells ensures reliable isolation of aquifers and geological layers during the stimulation of the shale formation and the operation of the wells. All casing strings installed within the well are cemented to the surface.

The selected steel grade and diameter of the production casing string must satisfy the requirements necessary for conducting perforation operations within the well and for executing hydraulic fracturing of the layer. Throughout the development of the argillite formation, observation wells are also drilled across the area to the depth of the first aquifer. The primary objective of the observation wells is to monitor and prevent contamination of the aquifer.

Technologies for shale gas extraction

Current technologies used include:

1. Hydraulic fracturing;
 - 1.1. With water;
 - 1.2. With liquefied gases;
 - 1.3 With inert gases;
2. Hydromechanical impact;

3. Multilateral drilling with horizontal sections and subsequent deep perforation.

The hydraulic fracturing method is fundamentally rooted in a process wherein a fluid is injected into the bottomhole zone of a well at high velocity, a quantity of which exceeds the absorption capacity of the geological formation. This results in an increase in bottomhole pressure, which, upon reaching a critical threshold, surpasses the pressure at which the rock maintains its structural integrity (Gerov, 2019). Consequently, the rock is fractured along planes characterised by minimal strength, leading to the formation of various crack types, including vertical and horizontal orientations. Figure 1 illustrates the hydraulic fracturing of the geological formation.

The initial implementation of hydraulic fracturing was recorded in 1947, executed in a gas well at the Hugoton gas field in the United States at a depth of 740 metres. To date, there have been over 400,000 gas wells in the United States where hydraulic fracturing has been performed. This milestone marked the beginning of extensive scientific, experimental, and industrial investigations aimed at the enhancement of hydraulic fracturing technologies.

In the context of domestic advancements, between 1967 and 1970, three experimental-industrial operations for hydraulic fracturing were conducted. The targeted formation was the Lower Triassic horizon, identified in the E-24 and E-26 wells located within the Chiren gas condensate field. Gas condensate served as the fracturing fluid, while a condensate-water emulsion was employed as the transporting fluid (Gerov, 2019).

Fig 1: Hydraulic fracturing illustration.

The fluids employed in hydraulic fracturing operations may include water-based liquids, hydrocarbon-based fluids, gas-liquid systems, and gaseous agents, such as liquefied hydrocarbon gas, nitrogen, and carbon dioxide. The utilisation of liquefied hydrocarbon gas, nitrogen, or carbon dioxide significantly reduces the reliance on large volumes of water and the need for subsequent wastewater treatment. Typically, over 1300 cubic meters of water are required for the hydraulic fracturing of a single well.

Figure 2 illustrates the composition of a water-based fracturing fluid. As indicated, the fluid comprises 99.2% water, with the remaining 0.79% consisting of chemical additives designed to reduce hydraulic resistance and regulate the pH of the fracturing environment.

Fig. 2. Composition of a water-based fluid used in hydraulic fracturing

To ensure that the induced fractures remain open after the bottom-hole pressure declines to pre-treatment levels, a proppant material is introduced. This reinforcing agent serves to stabilise the fractures and is generally composed of:

- Quartz sand fractions;
- Synthetic ceramic proppants;
- Medium-strength ceramic proppants.

Key Requirements for Hydraulic Fracturing Fluids:

1. They must be environmentally safe and should not contaminate the natural environment upon their return from the formation.

2. They should exhibit high thermal stability and retain their structural integrity during flow.
3. They must possess low corrosive activity.
4. They should be easily degradable after the completion of the operation, facilitating their recovery during well exploitation.
5. They must enable efficient transport of the proppant material throughout the fracture propagation process.
6. They should exhibit the required viscosity to ensure the creation of fractures with the designed length, height, and aperture.
7. They must be easily and reliably prepared during on-site operations.
8. They should have a relatively low cost of production.

Factors Determining the Appropriate Type of Fracturing Fluid (Gerov, 2019):

1. Type of hydraulic fracturing: local, conventional, deep, massive, or selective;
2. Type of reservoir;
3. Reservoir characteristics: permeability, porosity, and natural fracturing;
4. Physicomechanical properties of the reservoir rock;
5. Thermobaric (temperature and pressure) conditions.

Multilateral drilling with horizontal sections followed by gas-mechanical stimulation is expected to find extensive application in shale gas extraction.

Figure 3 illustrates multilateral drilling with horizontal sections from a single well pad, followed by gas-mechanical stimulation. This approach provides an expanded drainage area and enables large-scale stimulation through the application of multistage gas-mechanical treatments.

Fig. 3. Multilateral drilling with horizontal sections and subsequent deep perforation.

In this fracturing technique, the impact caused by the secondary high-pressure gas wave typically extends only a few meters from the wellbore. Gas-mechanical stimulation is primarily conducted in wells with horizontal sections.

For the development of shale gas fields, multilateral drilling can be applied using various well completion configurations, including stacked, dual, fishbone-type, radial, or hybrid designs (Georgiev, 2023).

Figure 4 presents a schematic diagram of the fishbone configuration.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of the fishbone configuration.

Modelling the initiation, control, and propagation of fractures in each specific case determines the optimal technology for developing gas fields that intersect argillite formations by enhancing the permeability of the argillite layer. To this end, modelling approaches are employed to solve two-dimensional problems for defining and controlling the spread and length of the induced fractures. The pressure at which formation fracturing occurs is primarily influenced by the following factors:

- the physico-mechanical properties of the rocks,
- the filtration characteristics of the reservoir rock,
- the distribution of geostatic pressure.

To evaluate the effectiveness of a hydraulic fracturing operation, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive set of well logging, geophysical, and hydro-gasodynamic tests.

The primary modern technical equipment used in implementing hydraulic fracturing technology includes high-pressure pumping units, mixers, a reservoir for the working fluid, a reservoir for wastewater generated after the operation, and a flare line. These components are connected to the wellhead via a manifold system. In contemporary setups, the entire process is managed and monitored through automated control systems.

In Northern Bulgaria, geological exploration studies have identified several areas suitable for shale gas exploration, associated with various lithostratigraphic units (Zaneva-Dobranova, 2012).

Conclusion

In addition to the technical and technological aspects of this issue, environmental risk assessment plays a critical role in the implementation of hydraulic fracturing technologies. The high level of advancement in technical and technological solutions in recent years enables the risk to be predicted, controlled, managed, and ultimately avoided. For each specific shale gas deposit, the technologies and technical means for development and exploitation must be adapted to the unique characteristics of the shale formation and the prevailing geological conditions.

In Bulgaria and its maritime zone in the Black Sea, it is essential to resume the exploration and investigation of unconventional energy resources, including shale gas. A reconsideration of the moratorium banning the application of hydraulic fracturing ("fracking") technologies in Bulgaria – adopted by the National Assembly on the grounds of presumed severe environmental harm – is necessary.

The adoption of this moratorium is counterproductive, particularly considering that the existing Subsurface Resources Act already prohibits the use of technologies that harm the environment, provided such harm is substantiated through environmental impact assessments and compatibility evaluations conducted by qualified experts.

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